

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Ceres Extended Juling (CXJ) (vir_da922)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da922 session. These operations were executed as part of the CXJ phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Ceres, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da922 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis *et al.*, "The VIR Spectrometer," *issr*, vol. 163, no. 1-4, pp. 329-369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C1Juling_1.r06.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C1Juling_1.r06.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C1Juling_1.r06.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_1	529939080	529939082	2
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOn_Oxo1	529939140	529939561	421
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_Oxo1	529939740	529950546	10806
VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_Oxo1	529950600	529952414	1814
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_Oxo1	529952700	529952740	40
VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_Oxo1	529952820	529955976	3156
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_Oxo1	529956000	529956038	38
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_Oxo1	529956120	529959720	3600
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_J01	529969980	529970020	40
VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01	529970100	529973241	3141
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_J01	529973280	529973318	38
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J01	529973400	529973407	7
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J01	529973520	529978920	5400
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_J01	529980540	529980840	300
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOn_Oxo2	530008580	530009001	421
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_Oxo2	530009180	530019986	10806
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_Oxo2	530020040	530020080	40
VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_Oxo2	530020160	530023316	3156
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_Oxo2	530023340	530023378	38
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_Oxo2	530023460	530027060	3600
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_J02	530037440	530037480	40
VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02	530037560	530040701	3141
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_J02	530040740	530040778	38
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J02	530040860	530040867	7
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J02	530040980	530046380	5400
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_J02	530048000	530048300	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_1	530048360	530048361	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C1Juling_2.r06.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C1Juling_2.r06.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

2.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C1Juling_2.r06.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_2	530280762	530280764	2
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOn_006	530280822	530281243	421
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_006	530281422	530292228	10806
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_006	530292282	530292322	40
VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006	530292402	530297214	4812
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_006	530297262	530297300	38
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_006	530297382	530297389	7
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_006	530297502	530302902	5400
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_006	530302902	530303202	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_2	530303262	530303263	1

2.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

3. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C1Juling_3.r07.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C1Juling_3.r07.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

3.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C1Juling_3.r07.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_3	530350622	530350624	2
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOn_007	530350682	530351103	421
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_007	530351282	530362088	10806
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_007	530362142	530362182	40
VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007	530362262	530364668	2406
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_007a	530364672	530364710	38
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_007a	530380142	530380182	40
VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007	530380262	530382653	2391
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_007	530382662	530382700	38
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_007	530382782	530382789	7
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_007	530382902	530388302	5400
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_007	530388302	530388602	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_3	530388662	530388663	1

3.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

4. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C1Juling_4.r08.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C1Juling_4.r08.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

4.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C1Juling_4.r08.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_4	530416882	530416884	2
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOn_008	530416942	530417363	421
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_008	530417542	530428348	10806
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_008	530428402	530428442	40
VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008	530428522	530430928	2406
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_008a	530430932	530430970	38
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_008a	530447002	530447042	40
VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008	530447122	530449513	2391
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_008	530449522	530449560	38
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_008	530449642	530449649	7
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_008	530449762	530455162	5400
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_008	530455162	530455462	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_4	530455522	530455523	1

4.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

5. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C1Juling_5.r05.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C1Juling_5.r05.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

5.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C1Juling_5.r05.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_5	530486742	530486744	2
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOn_009	530486802	530487223	421
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_009	530487402	530498208	10806
VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_009	530498262	530498302	40
VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009	530498382	530503194	4812
VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_009	530503242	530503280	38
VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_009	530503362	530503369	7
VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_009	530503482	530508882	5400
VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_009	530508882	530509182	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_5	530509242	530509243	1

5.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

6. Integrated sequence: da922d.01.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da922d.01.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 36 cubes for IR channel and 0 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

7. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

7.1 The sequence: vir_cxj_C1Juling_1.r06.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C1Juling_1.r06.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-273T16:16:47.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C1Juling_1.r06;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Thu Sep 29 16:16:47 2016
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2016-281T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_CXJ_da922_Cycle1_ds822
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_013, 2016-291T07:55:00.000
26 *CXJ_DEQUAX_014, 2016-292T02:49:20.000
27 *CXJ_VIRC01_J01, CXJ_DEQUAX_013+02:00:00
28 *CXJ_VIRC01_J02, CXJ_DEQUAX_014+01:50:00
29 *CXJ_VIRC01_0x01, CXJ_DEQUAX_013-02:48:00
30 *CXJ_VIRC01_0x02, CXJ_DEQUAX_014-03:00:00
31 *EPOCHS_END
32 *Input files used:
33 *File Type  Last modified      File name
34 *****
35 $$EOH
36 $$EOD

```

```

37
38 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_1,
39         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1-03:49:00,
40         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C1Juling_1 (ds822)",
41         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
42         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
43         KEY, "No_Key")
44
45     activity(1,
46         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
47
48         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds822","ds822.mc
49         fb04")
50     ),
51     note(1,
52         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
53         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds822 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_1"\
54     ),
55 end;
56
57 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_0xo1,
58         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1-03:48:00,
59         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
60         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
61         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
62         KEY, "No_Key")
63
64     spawn(1,
65         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
66         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
67         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
68     ),
69     note(1,
70         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
71         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_0xo1: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
72     ),
73 end;
74
75 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo1,
76         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1-03:38:00,
77         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
78         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
79         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
80         KEY, "No_Key")
81
82     command(1,
83         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
84         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
85         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
86     ),
87     command(2,
88         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
89         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo1: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
90         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
91     ),
92     note(1,
93         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

```

```
92     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo1: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
93     ),
94 end;
95
96 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1,
97     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1-00:37:00,
98     TITLE, \"VIR full calibration sequence\",
99     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
100    PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
101    KEY, \"No_Key\")
102
103    command(1,
104        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
105        NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
106        VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
107    ),
108    command(2,
109        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
110        NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: perform the internal full calibration"\,
111        VIR_CALIBRATION(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\", \"CLOSECOVERATEND\", \"FULLCALSEQ\")
112    ),
113    command(3,
114        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
115        NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: select VIR on 1553 bus"\,
116        XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT(\"VIR\")
117    ),
118    command(4,
119        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
120        NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
121        VIR_MM_DUMP(\"NO_COMPRESSION\")
122    ),
123    command(5,
124        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125        NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
126        VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
127    ),
128    note(1,
129        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
130        TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: full calibration is finished."\"
131    ),
132    note(2,
133        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
134        TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CalibrationDump_0xo1: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960
135        packets."\"
136    ),
137 end;
138 request(VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_0xo1,
139     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1-00:02:00,
140     TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
141     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
142     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
143     KEY, \"No_Key\")
144
145    activity(1,
146        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
147        NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_0xo1: Set for opening the cover."\",
```

```

148     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
149     ),
150 end;
151
152 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1,
153     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1+00:00:00,
154     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
155     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
156     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
157     KEY, "No_Key")
158
159     command(1,
160         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
161         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
162         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
163     ),
164     command(2,
165         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
166         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
167         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
168     ),
169     command(3,
170         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
171         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
172         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
173         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
174     ),
175     command(4,
176         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
177         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
178         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
179     ),
180     note(1,
181         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
182         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.115 Gbit"\
183     ),
184     command(5,
185         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
187         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
188     ),
189     command(6,
190         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
191         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
192         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
193     ),
194     command(7,
195         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
196         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
197         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
198         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
199     ),

```

```

200     command(8,
201         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
202         NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
203         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
204     ),
205     note(2,
206         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
207         TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit\"\\
208     ),
209     command(9,
210         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
211         NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
212         to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
213         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-148500,144000,4500)
214     ),
215     command(10,
216         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
217         NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
218         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\"\\,
219         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,67,130,5,1,69,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",4,\"NO_VIR
220     ),
221     command(11,
222         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
223         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
224         NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
225         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
226     ),
227     command(12,
228         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
229         NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
230         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
231     ),
232     note(3,
233         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
234         TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo1: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
235     ),
236 end;
237
238 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_0xo1,
239     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1+00:53:00,
240     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
241     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
242     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
243     KEY, \"No_Key\")
244
245 activity(1,
246     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
247     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_0xo1: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
248     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
249 ),
250 end;
251
252 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo1,
253     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo1+00:55:00,
254     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
255     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
256     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",

```

```

255     KEY, "No_Key")
256
257     command(1,
258         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
259         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
260         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo1: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
261         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
262     ),
263     command(2,
264         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
265         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo1: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
266         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
267     ),
268     note(1,
269         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
270         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo1: data volume in VR4 0.485 Gbit."\"
271     ),
272 end;
273
274 request(VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_J01,
275     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J01-00:02:00,
276     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
277     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
278     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
279     KEY, "No_Key")
280
281     activity(1,
282         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
283         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_J01: Set for opening the cover."\",
284         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
285     ),
286 end;
287
288 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01,
289     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J01+00:00:00,
290     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
291     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
292     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
293     KEY, "No_Key")
294
295     command(1,
296         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
297         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\",
298         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
299     ),
300     command(2,
301         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
302         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
303         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\",
304         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
305     ),
306     command(3,
307         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
308         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
309         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
310     ),

```

```

311     note(1,
312         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
313         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
314     ),
315     command(4,
316         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
317         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,100
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
318         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,100,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
319     ),
320     command(5,
321         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
322         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
323         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
324         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
325     ),
326     command(6,
327         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:25:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
328         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
329         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
330     ),
331     note(2,
332         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
333         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
334     ),
335     command(7,
336         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
337         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
338         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
339     ),
340     command(8,
341         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
342         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
343         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
344         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
345     ),
346     command(9,
347         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
348         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
349         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
350     ),
351     note(3,
352         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
353         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J01: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
354     ),
355 end;
356
357 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_J01,
358     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J01+00:53:00,
359     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
360     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
361     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
362     KEY, "No_Key")
363
364 activity(1,

```

```
365     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
366     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_J01: Set for closing the cover."\\,
367     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
368   ),
369 end;
370
371 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J01,
372     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J01+00:55:00,
373     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
374     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
375     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
376     KEY, "No_Key")
377
378     command(1,
379     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
380     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J01: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
381     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
382   ),
383     command(2,
384     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
385     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J01: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\\,
386     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
387   ),
388     note(1,
389     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
390     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J01: the cryocooling is off."\\
391   ),
392 end;
393
394 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J01,
395     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J01+00:57:00,
396     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
397     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
398     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
399     KEY, "No_Key")
400
401     command(1,
402     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
403     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\\,
404     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J01: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
405     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
406   ),
407     command(2,
408     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
409     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J01: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
410     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
411   ),
412     note(1,
413     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
414     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J01: data volume in VR4 0.844 Gibit."\\
415   ),
416 end;
417
418 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_J01,
419     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J01+02:54:00,
420     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
421     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
```

```
422     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
423     KEY, "No_Key")
424
425     note(1,
426         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
427         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0ff_J01: Power off VIR instrument."\
428     ),
429     spawn(1,
430         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
431         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
432         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
433     ),
434     note(2,
435         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
436         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0ff_J01: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
437     ),
438 end;
439
440 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_0xo2,
441     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo2-03:13:00,
442     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
443     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
444     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
445     KEY, "No_Key")
446
447     spawn(1,
448         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
449         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
450         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
451     ),
452     note(1,
453         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
454         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_0xo2: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
455     ),
456 end;
457
458 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo2,
459     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo2-03:03:00,
460     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
461     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
462     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
463     KEY, "No_Key")
464
465     command(1,
466         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
467         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo2: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
468         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
469     ),
470     command(2,
471         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
472         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo2: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
473         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
474     ),
475     note(1,
476         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
477         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_0xo2: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
waiting."\  

```

```

478     ),
479 end;
480
481 request(VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_0xo2,
482     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo2-00:02:00,
483     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
484     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
485     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
486     KEY, "No_Key")
487
488     activity(1,
489     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
490     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_0xo2: Set for opening the cover." \,
491     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
492     ),
493 end;
494
495 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2,
496     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo2+00:00:00,
497     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
498     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
499     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
500     KEY, "No_Key")
501
502     command(1,
503     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
504     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps" \,
505     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22, -144000,139500,4500)
506     ),
507     command(2,
508     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
509     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s" \,
510     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66, "IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",4, "NO_VIR
511     ),
512     command(3,
513     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
514     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
515     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
516     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
517     ),
518     command(4,
519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
520     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
521     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
522     ),
523     note(1,
524     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
525     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.115 Gibit" \
526     ),
527     command(5,
528     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
529     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps" \,
530     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22, -144000,139500,4500)
531     ),

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532     command(6,
533         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
534         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
535         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
536     ),
537     command(7,
538         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
539         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
540         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
541         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
542     ),
543     command(8,
544         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
545         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
546         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
547     ),
548     note(2,
549         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
550         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit\"
551     ),
552     command(9,
553         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
554         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
555         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-148500,144000,4500)
556     ),
557     command(10,
558         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
559         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
560         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,67,130,5,1,69,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
561     ),
562     command(11,
563         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
564         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
565         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
566         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
567     ),
568     command(12,
569         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
570         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
571         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
572     ),
573     note(3,
574         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
575         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_0xo2: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"
576     ),
577 end;
578
579 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_0xo2,
580     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo2+00:53:00,
581     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
582     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
583     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
584     KEY, "No_Key")

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```
585
586     activity(1,
587         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
588         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_0xo2: Set for closing the cover." \,
589         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
590     ),
591 end;
592
593 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo2,
594     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_0xo2+00:55:00,
595     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
596     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
597     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
598     KEY, "No_Key")
599
600     command(1,
601         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
602         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000" \,
603         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo2: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
604         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
605     ),
606     command(2,
607         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
608         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo2: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
609         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
610     ),
611     note(1,
612         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
613         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_0xo2: data volume in VR4 1.203 Gibit." \
614     ),
615 end;
616
617 request(VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_J02,
618     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02-00:02:00,
619     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
620     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
621     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
622     KEY, "No_Key")
623
624     activity(1,
625         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
626         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_J02: Set for opening the cover." \,
627         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
628     ),
629 end;
630
631 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02,
632     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02+00:00:00,
633     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
634     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
635     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
636     KEY, "No_Key")
637
638     command(1,
639         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
640         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
        frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s" \,
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641     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
642 ),
643     command(2,
644         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
645         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
646         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
647         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
648     ),
649     command(3,
650         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
651         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
652         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
653     ),
654     note(1,
655         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
656         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
657     ),
658     command(4,
659         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
660         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,100
        frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
661         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,100,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
662 ),
663     command(5,
664         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
665         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
666         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
667         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
668     ),
669     command(6,
670         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:25:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
671         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
672         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
673     ),
674     note(2,
675         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
676         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
677     ),
678     command(7,
679         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
680         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
        frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
681         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
682 ),
683     command(8,
684         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
685         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
686         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
687         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
688     ),
689     command(9,
690         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
691         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
692         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
693     ),

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694     note(3,  
695         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
696         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_J02: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\  
697     ),  
698 end;  
699  
700 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_J02,  
701     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02+00:53:00,  
702     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",  
703     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
704     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
705     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
706  
707     activity(1,  
708         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
709         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_J02: Set for closing the cover.\"\  
710         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")  
711     ),  
712 end;  
713  
714 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J02,  
715     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02+00:55:00,  
716     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",  
717     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
718     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
719     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
720  
721     command(1,  
722         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
723         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J02: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
724         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
725     ),  
726     command(2,  
727         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
728         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J02: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\  
729         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)  
730     ),  
731     note(1,  
732         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
733         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_J02: the cryocooling is off.\"\  
734     ),  
735 end;  
736  
737 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J02,  
738     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02+00:57:00,  
739     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",  
740     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
741     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
742     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
743  
744     command(1,  
745         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
746         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\  
747         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J02: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\  
748         VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")  
749     ),  
750     command(2,
```

```

751     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
752     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J02: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
753     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
754   ),
755   note(1,
756     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
757     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_J02: data volume in VR4 1.562 Gibit." \
758   ),
759 end;
760
761 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_J02,
762   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02+02:54:00,
763   TITLE, "VIR Power off",
764   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
765   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
766   KEY, "No_Key")
767
768   note(1,
769     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
770     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_J02: Power off VIR instrument." \
771   ),
772   spawn(1,
773     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
774     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
775     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
776   ),
777   note(2,
778     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
779     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_J02: Power off VML sequence is finished;" \
780   ),
781 end;
782
783 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_1,
784   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_J02+03:00:00,
785   TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C1Juling_1 (ds822)",
786   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
787   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
788   KEY, "No_Key")
789
790   note(1,
791     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
792     TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds822 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_1" \
793   ),
794 end;
795
796 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.2 The sequence: vir_cxj_C1Juling_2.r06.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C1Juling_2.r06.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;

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```

8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-273T16:16:47.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C1Juling_2.r06;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$MARK$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Thu Sep 29 16:16:47 2016
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2016-281T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_CXJ_da922_Cycle1_ds823
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_018, 2016-295T06:26:42.000
26 *CXJ_VIRC01_006, CXJ_DEQUAX_018-03:00:00
27 *EPOCHS_END
28 *Input files used:
29 *File Type  Last modified          File name
30 *****
31 $$EOH
32 $$EOD
33
34 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_2,
35         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006-03:14:00,
36         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C1Juling_2 (ds823)",
37         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
38         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
39         KEY, "No_Key")
40
41     activity(1,
42         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
43
44         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds823","ds823.mc
45         fb05")
46     ),
47     note(1,
48         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
49         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds823 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_2" \
50     ),
51 end;
52
53 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_006,
54         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006-03:13:00,
55         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
56         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
57         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
58         KEY, "No_Key")
59
60     spawn(1,
61         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
62         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
63         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
64     ),
65     note(1,

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64     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
65     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_006: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
66     ),
67 end;
68
69 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_006,
70     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006-03:03:00,
71     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
72     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
73     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
74     KEY, "No_Key")
75
76     command(1,
77     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
78     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
79     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
80     ),
81     command(2,
82     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
83     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_006: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
84     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
85     ),
86     note(1,
87     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
88     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_006: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
89     waiting."\"
90     ),
91 end;
92
93 request(VIR_CXJ_C10penCover_006,
94     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006-00:02:00,
95     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
96     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
97     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
98     KEY, "No_Key")
99
100 activity(1,
101     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
102     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C10penCover_006: Set for opening the cover."\",
103     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
104     ),
105 end;
106
107 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006,
108     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006+00:00:00,
109     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
110     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
111     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
112     KEY, "No_Key")
113
114     command(1,
115     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
116     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
117     to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\",
118     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
119     ),
120     command(2,
```

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120 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
    frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\",
121 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
122 ),
123 command(3,
124 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\",
126 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
127 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
128 ),
129 command(4,
130 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
131 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
132 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
133 ),
134 note(1,
135 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
136 TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit\"
137 ),
138 command(5,
139 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
    to perform 48 scan mirror steps\",
141 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
142 ),
143 command(6,
144 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
145 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
    frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\",
146 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
147 ),
148 command(7,
149 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
150 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\",
151 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
152 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
153 ),
154 command(8,
155 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
156 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
157 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
158 ),
159 note(2,
160 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
161 TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"
162 ),
163 command(9,
164 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
165 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
    to perform 48 scan mirror steps\",
166 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
167 ),
168 command(10,
169 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
170 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
    frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\",

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171     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIF
172 ),
173     command(11,
174     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
175     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
176     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
177     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
178 ),
179     command(12,
180     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
181     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
182     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
183 ),
184     note(3,
185     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
187 ),
188     command(13,
189     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
191     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
192 ),
193     command(14,
194     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
195     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
196     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIF
197 ),
198     command(15,
199     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
200     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
201     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
202     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
203 ),
204     command(16,
205     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
206     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
207     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
208 ),
209     note(4,
210     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
211     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
212 ),
213     command(17,
214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
215     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
216     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
217 ),
218     command(18,
219     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
220     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
221     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIF

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222     ),
223     command(19,
224         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
226         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
227         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
228     ),
229     command(20,
230         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
231         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
232         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
233     ),
234     note(5,
235         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
236         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\
237     ),
238     command(21,
239         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
240         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
241         to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
242         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
243     ),
244     command(22,
245         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
246         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
247         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
248         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
249     ),
250     command(23,
251         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
252         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
253         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
254         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
255     ),
256     command(24,
257         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
259         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
260     ),
261     note(6,
262         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_006: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
264     ),
265     end;
266     request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_006,
267         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006+01:21:00,
268         TITLE, "VIR cclose cover",
269         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
270         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
271         KEY, "No_Key")
272     activity(1,
273         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
274         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_006: Set for closing the cover."\",
275         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
276     ),

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277 end;
278
279 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_006,
280         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006+01:23:00,
281         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
282         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
283         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
284         KEY, "No_Key")
285
286     command(1,
287             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
288             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
289             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
290         ),
291     command(2,
292             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
293             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_006: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
294             VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
295         ),
296     note(1,
297         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
298         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_006: the cryocooling is off." \
299     ),
300 end;
301
302 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_006,
303         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006+01:25:00,
304         TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
305         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
306         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
307         KEY, "No_Key")
308
309     command(1,
310             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
311             COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000" \,
312             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_006: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
313             VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
314         ),
315     command(2,
316             SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
317             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
318             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
319         ),
320     note(1,
321         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
322         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_006: data volume in VR4 0.539 Gibit." \
323     ),
324 end;
325
326 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_006,
327         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006+02:55:00,
328         TITLE, "VIR Power off",
329         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
330         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
331         KEY, "No_Key")
332
333     note(1,
```

```

334     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
335     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_006: Power off VIR instrument." \
336   ),
337   spawn(1,
338     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
339     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
340     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
341   ),
342   note(2,
343     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
344     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_006: Power off VML sequence is finished;" \
345   ),
346 end;
347
348 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_2,
349   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_006+03:01:00,
350   TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C1Juling_2 (ds823)",
351   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
352   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
353   KEY, "No_Key")
354
355   note(1,
356     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
357     TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds823 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_2" \
358   ),
359 end;
360
361 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.3 The sequence: vir_cxj_C1Juling_3.r07.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C1Juling_3.r07.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-273T16:16:48.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C1Juling_3.r07;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN     SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Thu Sep 29 16:16:48 2016
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2016-281T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_CXJ_da922_Cycle1_ds824
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_019, 2016-296T01:21:02.000

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26 *CXJ_VIRC01_007, CXJ_DEQUAX_019-02:30:00
27 *EPOCHS_END
28 *Input files used:
29 *File Type Last modified File name
30 *****
31 $$EOH
32 $$EOD
33
34 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_3,
35         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007-03:14:00,
36         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C1Juling_3 (ds824)",
37         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
38         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
39         KEY, "No_Key")
40
41     activity(1,
42             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
43             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE", "ds824", "ds824.mc
fb04")
44     ),
45     note(1,
46         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
47         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds824 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_3" \
48     ),
49 end;
50
51 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_007,
52         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007-03:13:00,
53         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
54         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
55         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
56         KEY, "No_Key")
57
58     spawn(1,
59         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
60         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
61         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on, "VIR_P", "SAFE")
62     ),
63     note(1,
64         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
65         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_007: Power on VML sequence is finished;" \
66     ),
67 end;
68
69 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_007,
70         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007-03:03:00,
71         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
72         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
73         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
74         KEY, "No_Key")
75
76     command(1,
77         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
78         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
79         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
80     ),
81     command(2,
```

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82     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
83     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_007: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\\,
84     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
85     ),
86     note(1,
87     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
88     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_007: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
89     waiting."\\
90     ),
91     end;
92     request(VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_007,
93     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007-00:02:00,
94     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
95     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
96     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
97     KEY, "No_Key")
98
99     activity(1,
100    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
101    NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_007: Set for opening the cover."\\,
102    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
103    ),
104    end;
105
106    request(VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007,
107    START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+00:00:00,
108    TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
109    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
110    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
111    KEY, "No_Key")
112
113    command(1,
114    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
115    NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
116    to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\\,
117    VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
118    ),
119    command(2,
120    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
121    NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
122    frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\\,
123    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
124    ),
125    command(3,
126    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
127    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
128    NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
129    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
130    ),
131    command(4,
132    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
133    NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
134    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
135    ),
136    note(1,
137    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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136     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
137   ),
138   command(5,
139     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
141     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
142   ),
143   command(6,
144     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
145     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
146     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
147   ),
148   command(7,
149     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
150     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
151     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
152     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
153   ),
154   command(8,
155     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
156     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
157     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
158   ),
159   note(2,
160     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
161     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
162   ),
163   command(9,
164     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
165     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
166     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
167   ),
168   command(10,
169     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
170     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
171     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
172   ),
173   command(11,
174     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
175     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
176     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
177     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
178   ),
179   command(12,
180     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
181     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
182     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
183   ),
184   note(3,
185     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_007: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
187   ),

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188 end;
189
190 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_007a,
191         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+00:40:10,
192         TITLE, "VIR close cover",
193         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
194         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
195         KEY, "No_Key")
196
197     activity(1,
198             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
199             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_007a: Set for closing the cover." \,
200             VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
201     ),
202 end;
203
204 request(VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_007a,
205         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+04:58:00,
206         TITLE, "VIR open cover",
207         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
208         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
209         KEY, "No_Key")
210
211     activity(1,
212             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
213             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1OpenCover_007a: Set for opening the cover." \,
214             VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
215     ),
216 end;
217
218 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007,
219         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+05:00:00,
220         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
221         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
222         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
223         KEY, "No_Key")
224
225     command(1,
226             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
227             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s" \,
228             VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
229     ),
230     command(2,
231             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
232             COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
233             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
234             VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
235     ),
236     command(3,
237             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
238             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
239             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
240     ),
241     note(1,
242             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
243             TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit" \
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244     ),
245     command(4,
246         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
247         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
248         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
249     ),
250     command(5,
251         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
252         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
253         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
254         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
255     ),
256     command(6,
257         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
259         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
260     ),
261     note(2,
262         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\
264     ),
265     command(7,
266         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
267         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
268         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
269     ),
270     command(8,
271         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
272         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
273         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
274         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
275     ),
276     command(9,
277         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
278         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
279         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
280     ),
281     note(3,
282         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
283         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
284     ),
285 end;
286
287 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_007,
288     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+05:40:00,
289     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
290     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
291     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
292     KEY, "No_Key")
293
294 activity(1,
295     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
296     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_007: Set for closing the cover."\,
297     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")

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298     ),
299 end;
300
301 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_007,
302     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+05:42:00,
303     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
304     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
305     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
306     KEY, "No_Key")
307
308     command(1,
309     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
310     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
311     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
312     ),
313     command(2,
314     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
315     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_007: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
316     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
317     ),
318     note(1,
319     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
320     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_007: the cryocooling is off." \
321     ),
322 end;
323
324 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_007,
325     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+05:44:00,
326     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
327     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
328     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
329     KEY, "No_Key")
330
331     command(1,
332     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
333     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000" \,
334     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_007: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
335     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
336     ),
337     command(2,
338     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
339     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
340     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
341     ),
342     note(1,
343     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
344     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_007: data volume in VR4 0.539 Gibit." \
345     ),
346 end;
347
348 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_007,
349     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+07:14:00,
350     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
351     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
352     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
353     KEY, "No_Key")
354
```

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355     note(1,
356         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
357         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_007: Power off VIR instrument."\
358     ),
359     spawn(1,
360         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
361         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
362         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
363     ),
364     note(2,
365         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
366         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_007: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
367     ),
368 end;
369
370 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_3,
371     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_007+07:20:00,
372     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C1Juling_3 (ds824)",
373     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
374     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
375     KEY, "No_Key")
376
377     note(1,
378         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
379         TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds824 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_3"\
380     ),
381 end;
382
383 $$E0F

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.4 The sequence: vir_cxj_C1Juling_4.r08.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C1Juling_4.r08.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-273T16:16:49.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C1Juling_4.r08;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN     SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Thu Sep 29 16:16:49 2016
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2016-281T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_CXJ_da922_Cycle1_ds825
24 *EPOCHS_DEF

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25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_020, 2016-296T20:15:22.000
26 *CXJ_VIRC01_008, CXJ_DEQUAX_020-03:00:00
27 *EPOCHS_END
28 *Input files used:
29 *File Type Last modified File name
30 *****
31 $$EOH
32 $$EOD
33
34 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_4,
35         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008-03:14:00,
36         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C1Juling_4 (ds825)",
37         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
38         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
39         KEY, "No_Key")
40
41     activity(1,
42             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
43             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE", "ds825", "ds825.mc
44             fb05")
45             ),
46             note(1,
47                 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
48                 TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds825 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_4" \
49             ),
50             end;
51 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_008,
52         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008-03:13:00,
53         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
54         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
55         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
56         KEY, "No_Key")
57
58     spawn(1,
59           SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
60           REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
61           RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
62           ),
63           note(1,
64               SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
65               TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_008: Power on VML sequence is finished;" \
66           ),
67           end;
68
69 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_008,
70         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008-03:03:00,
71         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
72         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
73         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
74         KEY, "No_Key")
75
76     command(1,
77             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
78             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
79             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
80             ),
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81     command(2,
82         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
83         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_008: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\\,
84         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
85     ),
86     note(1,
87         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
88         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_008: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
89         waiting."\\
90     ),
91 end;
92 request(VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_008,
93     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008-00:02:00,
94     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
95     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
96     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
97     KEY, "No_Key")
98
99     activity(1,
100         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
101         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_008: Set for opening the cover."\\,
102         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
103     ),
104 end;
105
106 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008,
107     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+00:00:00,
108     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
109     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
110     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
111     KEY, "No_Key")
112
113     command(1,
114         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
115         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
116         to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\\,
117         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
118     ),
119     command(2,
120         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
121         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
122         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\\,
123         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
124     ),
125     command(3,
126         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
127         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
128         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
129         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
130     ),
131     command(4,
132         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
133         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
134         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
135     ),
136     note(1,

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135     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
136     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
137   ),
138   command(5,
139     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
141     to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
142     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
143   ),
144   command(6,
145     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
146     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
147     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
148     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
149   ),
150   command(7,
151     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
152     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
153     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
154     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
155   ),
156   command(8,
157     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
159     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
160   ),
161   note(2,
162     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
163     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
164   ),
165   command(9,
166     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
168     to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
169     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
170   ),
171   command(10,
172     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
174     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
175     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
176   ),
177   command(11,
178     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
179     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
180     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
181     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
182   ),
183   command(12,
184     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
185     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
186     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
187   ),
188   note(3,
189     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_008: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\

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187     ),
188 end;
189
190 request(VIR_CXJ_C1closeCover_008a,
191     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+00:40:10,
192     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
193     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
194     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
195     KEY, "No_Key")
196
197     activity(1,
198     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
199     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1closeCover_008a: Set for closing the cover."\,
200     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
201     ),
202 end;
203
204 request(VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_008a,
205     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+05:08:00,
206     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
207     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
208     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
209     KEY, "No_Key")
210
211     activity(1,
212     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
213     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_008a: Set for opening the cover."\,
214     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
215     ),
216 end;
217
218 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008,
219     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+05:10:00,
220     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
221     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
222     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
223     KEY, "No_Key")
224
225     command(1,
226     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
227     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
228     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
229     ),
230     command(2,
231     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
232     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
233     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
234     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
235     ),
236     command(3,
237     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
238     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
239     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
240     ),
241     note(1,
242     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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243     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
244 ),
245     command(4,
246         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
247         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
248         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
249     ),
250     command(5,
251         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
252         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
253         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
254         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
255     ),
256     command(6,
257         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
259         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
260     ),
261     note(2,
262         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\
264     ),
265     command(7,
266         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
267         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
268         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
269     ),
270     command(8,
271         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
272         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
273         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
274         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
275     ),
276     command(9,
277         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
278         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
279         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
280     ),
281     note(3,
282         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
283         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
284     ),
285 end;
286
287 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_008,
288     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+05:50:00,
289     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
290     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
291     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
292     KEY, "No_Key")
293
294 activity(1,
295     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
296     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_008: Set for closing the cover.""\,

```

```
297     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
298     ),
299 end;
300
301 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_008,
302     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+05:52:00,
303     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
304     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
305     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
306     KEY, "No_Key")
307
308     command(1,
309         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
310         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
311         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
312     ),
313     command(2,
314         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
315         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_008: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\",
316         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
317     ),
318     note(1,
319         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
320         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_008: the cryocooling is off."\"
321     ),
322 end;
323
324 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_008,
325     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+05:54:00,
326     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
327     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
328     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
329     KEY, "No_Key")
330
331     command(1,
332         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
333         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\",
334         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_008: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
335         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
336     ),
337     command(2,
338         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
339         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
340         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
341     ),
342     note(1,
343         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
344         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_008: data volume in VR4 0.539 Gibit."\"
345     ),
346 end;
347
348 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_008,
349     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+07:24:00,
350     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
351     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
352     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
353     KEY, "No_Key")
```

```

354
355     note(1,
356         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
357         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_008: Power off VIR instrument." \
358     ),
359     spawn(1,
360         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
361         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
362         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
363     ),
364     note(2,
365         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
366         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_008: Power off VML sequence is finished;" \
367     ),
368 end;
369
370 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_4,
371     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_008+07:30:00,
372     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C1Juling_4 (ds825)",
373     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
374     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
375     KEY, "No_Key")
376
377     note(1,
378         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
379         TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds825 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_4" \
380     ),
381 end;
382
383 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.5 The sequence: vir_cxj_C1Juling_5.r05.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C1Juling_5.r05.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-273T16:16:49.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C1Juling_5.r05;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN     SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Thu Sep 29 16:16:49 2016
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2016-281T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_CXJ_da922_Cycle1_ds826

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```
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_021, 2016-297T15:09:42.000
26 *CXJ_VIRC01_009, CXJ_DEQUAX_021-02:30:00
27 *EPOCHS_END
28 *Input files used:
29 *File Type Last modified File name
30 *****
31 $$EOH
32 $$EOD
33
34 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C1Juling_5,
35         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009-03:14:00,
36         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C1Juling_5 (ds826)",
37         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
38         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
39         KEY, "No_Key")
40
41     activity(1,
42             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
43             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE", "ds826", "ds826.mc
44             fb04")
45             ),
46             note(1,
47                 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
48                 TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds826 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_5" \
49             ),
50             end;
51 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_009,
52         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009-03:13:00,
53         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
54         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
55         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
56         KEY, "No_Key")
57
58     spawn(1,
59           SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
60           REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
61           RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
62           ),
63           note(1,
64               SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
65               TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Power0n_009: Power on VML sequence is finished;" \
66           ),
67           end;
68
69 request(VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_009,
70         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009-03:03:00,
71         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
72         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
73         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
74         KEY, "No_Key")
75
76     command(1,
77             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
78             NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1Cryocooler0n_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
79             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
```

```

80     ),
81     command(2,
82         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
83         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_009: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
84         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
85     ),
86     note(1,
87         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
88         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOn_009: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
89         waiting." \
90     ),
91 end;
92 request(VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_009,
93     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009-00:02:00,
94     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
95     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
96     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
97     KEY, "No_Key")
98
99     activity(1,
100         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
101         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1openCover_009: Set for opening the cover." \,
102         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
103     ),
104 end;
105
106 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009,
107     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009+00:00:00,
108     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
109     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
110     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
111     KEY, "No_Key")
112
113     command(1,
114         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
115         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
116         to perform 48 scan mirror steps" \,
117         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
118     ),
119     command(2,
120         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
121         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
122         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s" \,
123         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIF
124     ),
125     command(3,
126         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
127         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
128         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
129         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
130     ),
131     command(4,
132         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
133         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
134         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
135     ),

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134     note(1,
135         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
136         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
137     ),
138     command(5,
139         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
141         to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
142         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
143     ),
144     command(6,
145         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
146         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
147         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
148         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
149     ),
150     command(7,
151         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
152         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
153         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
154         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
155     ),
156     command(8,
157         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
159         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
160     ),
161     note(2,
162         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
163         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
164     ),
165     command(9,
166         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
168         to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
169         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
170     ),
171     command(10,
172         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
174         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
175         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
176     ),
177     command(11,
178         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
179         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
180         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
181         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
182     ),
183     command(12,
184         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
185         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
186         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
187     ),
188     note(3,
189         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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186     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
187   ),
188   command(13,
189     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
191     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
192   ),
193   command(14,
194     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
195     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
196     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
197   ),
198   command(15,
199     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
200     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
201     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
202     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
203   ),
204   command(16,
205     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
206     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
207     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
208   ),
209   note(4,
210     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
211     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
212   ),
213   command(17,
214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
215     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
216     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
217   ),
218   command(18,
219     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
220     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
221     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
222   ),
223   command(19,
224     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
226     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
227     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
228   ),
229   command(20,
230     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
231     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
232     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
233   ),
234   note(5,
235     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
236     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\
237   ),

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238     command(21,
239         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
240         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 48 scan mirror steps"\,
241         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-108000,103500,4500)
242     ),
243     command(22,
244         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
245         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
246         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
247     ),
248     command(23,
249         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
250         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
251         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
252         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
253     ),
254     command(24,
255         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
256         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
257         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
258     ),
259     note(6,
260         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
261         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CubeToVIR_009: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
262     ),
263 end;
264
265 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_009,
266     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009+01:21:00,
267     TITLE, "VIR cclose cover",
268     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
269     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
270     KEY, "No_Key")
271
272 activity(1,
273     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
274     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CloseCover_009: Set for closing the cover.""\,
275     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
276     ),
277 end;
278
279 request(VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_009,
280     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009+01:23:00,
281     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
282     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
283     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
284     KEY, "No_Key")
285
286 command(1,
287     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
288     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
289     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
290     ),
291     command(2,
292         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

```

```
293     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_009: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\",
294     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
295   ),
296   note(1,
297     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
298     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1CryocoolerOff_009: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
299   ),
300 end;
301
302 request(VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_009,
303   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009+01:25:00,
304   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
305   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
306   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
307   KEY, \"No_Key\")
308
309   command(1,
310     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
311     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
312     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_009: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
313     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
314   ),
315   command(2,
316     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
317     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
318     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
319   ),
320   note(1,
321     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
322     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1DumpDataToVR4_009: data volume in VR4 0.539 Gibit.\"\\
323   ),
324 end;
325
326 request(VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_009,
327   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009+02:55:00,
328   TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
329   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
330   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
331   KEY, \"No_Key\")
332
333   note(1,
334     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
335     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_009: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
336   ),
337   spawn(1,
338     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
339     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
340     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
341   ),
342   note(2,
343     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
344     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C1PowerOff_009: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\\
345   ),
346 end;
347
348 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C1Juling_5,
349   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC01_009+03:01:00,
```

```
350     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C1Juling_5 (ds826)",
351     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
352     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
353     KEY, "No_Key")
354
355     note(1,
356         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
357         TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds826 - vir_cxj_C1Juling_5"\
358     ),
359 end;
360
361 $$EOF
```